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Submitted by Nathan Bossa, Camilla Delpivo, Socorro Vázquez-Campos (LEITAT), Antreas Afantitis, Georgia Melagraki, Andreas Tsoumanis (NovaM), Periklis Tsiros, Harry Sarimveis (NTUA)

Revised by Thomas Exner (7P9) and Anastasios Papadiamantis (UoB)

Approved by Iseult Lynch (UoB)

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Abbreviations

ADME: Adsorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion
AO: Adverse Outcome
AOP: Adverse Outcome Pathway
BMD: Benchmark Dose
DLS: Dynamic Light Scattering
ECETOC: European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals
FF: Far Field
FSLVs : Final Safety Limit Values
HT: High Toxicity
KB: Knowledge Base
LDH: Lactate Dehydrogenase
LT: Low Toxicity
MOA: Mechanism-of-Action
MPC: Model Predictive Controller
MWCNT: Multi Wall Carbon Nanotube
NEP: Nano Enable Product
NF: Near Field
NFs: NanoForms
NMs: Nanomaterials
PBPK: Physiologically-Based Pharmacokinetic (model)
PEC: Predicted Environmental Concentrations
POD: Point Of Departure
PPE: Personal Protective Equipment
PtD: Prevention through Design
QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship
RA: Risk Assessment
RCR: Risk Characterisation Ratio
RM: Risk Management
RPs: Reference Points
SbD : Safe by Design
SbPC: Safe by Design Process Control
SPD: Spatial Data File
SR: Surface Reductibility
TA: Transcriptional Access
TEM: Transmission Electron Microscopy
VHT: Very High Toxicity
VLT: Very Low Toxicity
WWTP: WasteWater Treatment Plant

Summary

Design of safe and functional nanomaterials (NMs) is core to the field of nanosafety, and as such lessons learned regarding the drivers of NMs toxicity need to be fed back to NMs developers to support the design and development of improved NMs that can avoid specific features found to correlate with toxicity. Thus, one of the core goals of NanoCommons is to develop tools that support integration of nanosafety knowledge and facilitate the design of safe NMs. Here, in deliverable D6.4, we describe the Safe by Design (SbD) strategy that developed in completed and currently running European projects and review the progress towards implementation of the SbD concepts in the innovation process of different industrial sectors, and identify what is already provided to the community and what is still missing. Having identified the gaps, the NanoCommons consortium developed and strengthened the existing approaches and packaged them as an accessible and user-friendly tool to support the ongoing SbD projects.

The Deliverable thus provides a non-exhaustive presentation of the current state of the art in the NMs SbD field and a description of the tools and methodologies developed to-date to support the SbD objectives. Having assessed the current state of the art, the main body of the deliverable summarises the tools developed within NanoCommons and made available in the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase (KB) to support the ongoing work of the SbD cluster of projects and NMs SME producers and pilot lines projects who are scaling up the manufacture of NMs for a range of applications. A strong focus has been placed on further developing the existing computational tools and infrastructure to the level that they can be technically integrated to create a complete set of tools for SbD. Worked examples were developed to exemplify how the tools can be used.

The tools developed within NanoCommons to support SbD can be grouped as:

1. Tools to retrieve and compile information from databases for further use in SbD tools.
2. Tools for grouping of NMs
3. Predictive models available through the Jaqpot and Enalos platforms supporting the concept of Safer Product Design.
4. The integrated NanoCommons Risk Assessment (RA) workflow, presented in D6.1 and D6.3, focussing on how it supports the concept of Safer Process Design.

The current deliverable D6.4 presents all these new developments with a description of the tools and methods available, and an example of SbD strategy implementation in different NM and product cases. It also demonstrates that these tools can be technically integrated towards the development and implementation of complex workflows and analysis applications, which are useful for stakeholders involved in the safety assessment of NMs and the design of NMs-products and processes. The complete documentation of the models and the approaches, including the underpinning datasets, is a critical aspect of their acceptance by users and regulators, and as such is a key part of the dissemination of the models.

1. Introduction

Safe and sustainable innovation requires a good understanding of the potential health and environmental risks along the life cycle of a product. Compared with standard chemical risk assessment (RA), NM risk assessment is highly challenging, due to more complex nanoscale material structures and the limited experience in data generation, data management and modelling. The wide variety of NMs on the market, and the newly developed or emerging ones, substantially increase the number of applications. Therefore the expected human and environmental health risks may vary profoundly for different NMs in the different exposure scenarios that may occur during the life cycle of nano-enabled products (NEPs). Consequently, developing and integrating policies and methods for safe by design (SbD) and risk management (RM) of NMs is a priority for safe innovation to proceed and to facilitate ongoing commercialisation of nanotechnologies. SbD approaches aim to eliminate or reduce the risks of new technologies, such as nanotechnology, at the design stage of a product or at the production process. Anticipation of risks is challenging because some risks could emerge only after a technology is implemented (at later stages in the innovation process).

SbD is a concept that is well established in fields like construction, nuclear technology, water treatment, health facilities, and occupational health and safety. It describes safety measures for the prevention of accidents, illnesses, or environmental damage that are applied during the design stage of a facility, process, practice, material, or product. Generally, SbD is not new and has been used for years in industry. Various fields have adopted and developed different, but related concepts, all of which are based on the idea of designing products or processes that bear an intrinsically low-risk potential, instead of confining the potential risk by application of protective systems. Overall, SbD has to integrate the anticipated safety impacts of materials or products into the design and production phases. In the context of nanotechnology, SbD is a rather novel concept, aiming at the development of functional as well as safe NMs and nano-enabled products. The application of this concept requires:

- comprehensive knowledge questioning what property or properties makes a NM or nanoproduct more or less safe;
- means to implement this knowledge in a structured way into industrial innovation processes; and
- information exchange between the involved stakeholders.

The SbD concept, developed for classic pollutants, has been adapted to the NMs specific requirements and challenges in previous European projects (i.e., NanoREG¹, ProSafe², OPTINANOPRO³, and NanoREG2⁴) and approaches towards its implementation in the industrial innovation process are currently under development in ongoing European projects (see below for details). A recent publication summarised these efforts towards NMs safe by design (Table 1).

¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/310584>

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/646325>

³ <http://optinanopro.eu/>

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/646221>

Table 1. EU and national funded projects on safe by design, extracted from Rose *et al.* (2019).

Project title	Funding programme	Coordinator	Term	Project budget	Homepage
NANoREG A Common European Approach to the Regulatory Testing of Nanomaterials	FP7	Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Waterstaat, Netherlands	1.3.2013-28.2.2017	€ 49.586 mill. of which € 10 mill. EU funding	www.nanoreg.eu
NANoREG 2 Development and Implementation of Grouping and Safe-by-Design Approaches Within Regulatory Frameworks	Horizon 2020	Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques (INERIS), France	1.9.2015-31.8.2018	€ 11.933 mill. of which € 9.995 mill. EU funding	www.nanoreg2.eu
ProSafe Promoting the Implementation of Safe by Design	Horizon 2020	Ministerie van Infrastructuur en Waterstaat, Netherlands	1.02.2015-30.04.2017	€ 3.095 mill. of which € 2.512 mill. EU funding	n/a
NanoGenTools	Horizon 2020	Universidad de Burgos, Spain	1.01.2016-31.12.2019	€ 706.500 of which € 706.500 EU funding	www3.ubu.es/nanogentools/
NanoMile Engineered Nanomaterial Mechanisms of Interactions With Living Systems and the Environment: a Universal Framework for Safe Nanotechnology	FP7	The University of Birmingham, Great Britain	1.03.2013-28.02.2017	€ 12.965 mill. of which € 9.625 mill. EU funding	http://nanomile.eu-vri.eu/
NanoFase Nanomaterial Fate and Speciation in the Environment	Horizon 2020	Natural Environment Research Council, Great Britain	1.09.2015-31.08.2019	€ 11.297 mill. of which € 9.954 mill. EU funding	www.nanofase.eu/
EC4SafeNano European Centre for Risk Management and Safe Innovation in Nanomaterials & Nanotechnologies	Horizon 2020	Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques (INERIS), France	1.11.2016-31.10.2019	€ 1.999 mill. of which € 1.999 mill. EU funding	www.ec4safenano.eu
caLIBRAte Performance Testing, Calibration and Implementation of a Next Generation System-of-Systems Risk Governance Framework for Nanomaterials	Horizon 2020	Det Nationale Forskningscenter for Arbejdsmiljø, Denmark	1.05.2016-31.10.2019	€ 9.828 mill. of which € 7.999 mill. EU funding	www.nanocalibrate.eu/home
SafeNanoKap Applicability of the "Safe-by-Design" Concept – Case Study Development of Nanomaterials for Coffee Capsules	Nano-EHS	University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna – Institute of Waste Management	1.3.2017-28.2.2018	79,905 €	www.oeaw.ac.at/ita/projekte/safenanokap/ueberblick/
SbD-AT Relevance and Added Value for Austrian Companies	Nano-EHS	Brimatech Services GmbH	1.01.2017-31.12.2017	80,000 €	www.bionanonet.at/projects/sbd-at
Nano EHS SWOT SbD Nano EHS Strengths/Weaknesses Analysis "Safe-by-Design"	Nano-EHS	Austrian Institute of Technology	1.03.2017-28.02.2018	n/a	www.ait.ac.at/ueber-das-ait/center/center-for-innovation-systems-policy/nano-swot-sbd/

The Horizon 2020 call NMBP-15-2019 - Safe by design, from science to regulation: metrics and main sectors funded four projects: SAbYNA⁵, ASINA⁶, SAbYDOMA⁷, and SbD4Nano⁸. More recently three more projects were funded under the call NMBP-16-2020 (SbD of multicomponent EMNs), indicating that Europe will be working on establishing how to efficiently implement the SbD concept into practice and link this concept with regulation and industry. At the national level, the French funded SERENADE project, with its long-term funding scheme, provided a unique opportunity to foster a coordinated, yet diverse approach to investigate the SbD development of NMs in a variety of application fields, using a targeted set of interdisciplinary case studies (Rose *et al.*, 2021; Bottero *et al.*, 2017). Within NanoCommons, the challenge is to successfully streamline the tools available and developed to provide users easy, customized, and integrative guidance including all the resources (databases, test protocols, models, tools, frameworks etc.) to assess and manage the potential risks associated with nanotechnology-based products. Towards this goal, NanoCommons is working on connecting the infrastructure services with the SbD projects. The first steps toward this goal was done via

⁵ <https://www.sabyna.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.asina-project.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.sabydoma.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.sbd4nano.eu/>

collaboration with the projects SAbyNA and ASINA through Transnational Access (TA) applications. The data produced during these projects will flow into the NanoCommons KB and likewise the tools developed in these projects can pull data from the NanoCommons KB.

Multiple definitions of SbD for NMs have been provided by, for example, the JRC and European projects OptiNanoPro and NanoREG. NANoREG described the SbD Concept as *“Safe-by-Design: Identified, reduced and managed uncertainty and risks of innovative materials, products and processes at the time of market introduction”* and expanded this concept to NMs, presented in JRC Technical Reports - NANoREG harmonized terminology for environmental health and safety assessment of nanomaterials – 2016 (Laia *et al.*, 2016). The consensus at this time describes the SbD concept as *“The ‘safe by design’ concept aims at reducing potential health and environmental risks at an early phase of the innovation process. Such a concept aims at creating an integrated research strategy. This enables the consideration of safety aspects for humans and the environment in the design process of a product/material, to eliminate or minimize the risk of adverse effects during its life cycle including construction, use, maintenance, and deconstruction.*

Within the safe-by-design concept, the functionality of a NM and its toxicity/safety are therefore considered in an integrated way. Such an approach maximizes resource use and expedites the development of products containing NMs and new NMs that are safer by design.”

Kraegeloh *et al.* (2018) summarise the SbD concept developed by NanoReg2 and ProSafe and provide a comprehensive definition that aims to couple SbD to the regulatory process. The challenge of NanoReg2 was to build a regulatory system that was flexible enough to deal with new targets and requirements in the future, and this can be supported by the development and introduction of SbD principles. The credibility of such a regulatory system, underpinned by the implementation of SbD, is essential for industry, which accepts the need for regulation, but requires that this should be done cost-effectively and rapidly.

Another initiative from the NanoReg2 project was the creation of a workable Safe Innovation Approach (SIA) and SIA Toolbox⁹, which includes a set of tools, guidance, and checklists to be used by innovators and regulators along the innovation process. The SIA toolbox supports innovators and regulators by providing tools to deal with new safety issues of innovative NMs and NM-containing products; and providing regulatory preparedness. Users can query the SIA tools database according to the stage in the innovation process (*early, intermediate, advanced*), and the type of information needed (*Benefits, Costs, Risks*). SIA suggests a combination of the methods/tools that are already available to the users. Despite these recent efforts, the lack of suitable SbD tools with guidance and training support is still an issue hampering progress and widespread adoption of the process.

⁹ <https://siatoolbox.com>

2. Safe by Design approaches

2.1 Prevention through design approaches

Prevention through Design (PtD) involves all efforts to anticipate and design-out hazards to workers in facilities, work methods and operations, processes, equipment, tools, products, materials, new technologies, and the organization of work (Geraci *et al.*, 2015; NIOSH, 2009). PtD can be applied to nanotechnology at both the material and process levels. PtD, as per the traditional safety management plan, utilizes the traditional hierarchy of controls by focusing on hazard elimination and substitution followed by risk minimization through the application of engineering or administrative controls and finally, the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) during the activities (Geraci *et al.*, 2015; Peterson, 1973). These controls are described below.

Elimination/ substitution/ modification (Figure 1): Elimination is in most cases not an option and the substitution of one NM by another NM or by other materials with reduced toxicity is often difficult to achieve when considering costs and functionality. Therefore, the strategy can be to change the NMs property to reduce toxicity and obtain “acceptable” human and environmental toxicity. The main targeted physico-chemical parameters to modify are the size, shape, surface chemistry (described in later sections of this deliverable). When possible, the strategy is to modify the properties responsible for the toxicity considering the NMs route of exposure and the exposure population as well as the toxicity mechanism. The global idea is to reduce the NMs hazard while preserving its functionality. The research determining the mechanism of toxicity provides interesting input for finding specific strategies to reduce NMs’ hazards.

Figure 1. Illustration of the "prevention through design approach extracted from (Geraci *et al.*, 2015)"

Engineering controls: Besides the NMs modification, other parameters linked to the process can be adapted to reduce NMs exposure. Those parameters can be the use of ventilation, handling or performing processes involving NMs in an enclosed environment, reducing the process temperature or energy, etc. These types of risk management strategies are process-specific and sometimes can be sector-specific (i.e. paint, 3D printing, textile, plastics). To know where PtD is most needed it is important to determine which activities (exposure scenarios) pose the highest risks of exposure to toxic NMs. An example was extracted from a National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) industry-wide exposure assessment study of manufacturers and users of carbon nanotubes and nanofibers and the exposure potentials during each step in the process and potential exposure

reduction scenarios. Potential worker exposure was ranked as a function of each process involving powder handling (rank 1 as this was where the risk of inhalation was highest) and the impact of one simple strategy to reduce the worker exposure during this activity is to perform it in wet conditions - i.e., to use a slurry rather than a dry powder during pouring or other handling steps.

Administrative controls: this stage comes as one of the last resorts and is mostly considered as a minimal safety procedure to implement in occupational settings. As detailed elsewhere (Geraci *et al.*, 2015), an effective management system begins with an executive position statement that details all activities from bench scale to production. The project concept stage is the ideal time to establish EHS goals, identify potential hazards, and determine appropriate NM exposure control categories. Using a step-by-step approach to safe commercialization refines the decision-making process and enables the rational discovery of occupational hazards for elimination, modification, or control. The implementation of administrative controls is guided by a series of standard operating procedures (SOPs) and International Standardisation Organisation (ISO) standards. Other risk management strategies applied in the workplace include the practices for exposure monitoring and the use of personal protective equipment, as the last resort.

2.2 NanoREG Approach

Within the NANoREG project, the focus has been placed on the implementation of the concept of SbD towards the development of safer nano-enabled products. In this approach, the intended functionality and the safety aspects are considered at the product design stage and along the innovation process until the development phase. The NANoREG project focussed its efforts on integrating the SbD concept to a stage-gate model of innovation (Gottardo *et al.*, 2017). When innovations progress towards market application, information needs to be lined up in the direction of regulatory requirements. The NANoREG SbD approach hence includes the identification of the potential risks in the first stages of innovation, followed by indicators for risk at mid-stages of innovation, and by demonstrators for risks in the final stages of innovation, as shown in Figure 2. The goal is to anticipate potential human and environmental risks before the introduction of NMs or nano-enabled products in the market. The NANoREG SbD approach comprises: i) an innovation-stage dependent approach; ii) a strategy to identify nano-specific risks; iii) safe production of products/materials, safe use, safe end-of-life management. Whereas the concept can be applied to many different products, companies, and industries, for every product a new dataset is needed and needs to be accordingly structured.

Figure 2. Illustration of the "stage-gate innovation model" used as the backbone of the NanoReg Safe-by-Design (SbD) concept extracted from (Gottardo *et al.*, 2017).

2.3 Three pillars approach (NanoReg2 Approach)

In a recent publication Jiménez *et al.* (2020) tested the three pillars approach developed within the EU NanoReg2 and proSafe projects. A new concept was developed where SbD aims at identifying, estimating, and reducing uncertainties on human and environmental risks along the entire value chain, ideally starting at an early stage of the innovation process (Kraegeloh *et al.*, 2018; Soeteman-Hernandez *et al.*, 2019). This concept is built from the principle that an efficient safety strategy should be considered as an integral part of the design process (together with functionality and costs), rather than at a later stage once the process is already well advanced. SbD must thereby also include a sustainability assessment of the long-term ecological and economical impact (Salieri *et al.*, 2020). The three pillars are described as follows:

- ***Pillar 1- safer materials and products by design:*** This refers to identifying less hazardous NMs for humans and the environment and designing NEPs that, under normal and unforeseen conditions, do not release free NMs (unless that is a requirement for their performance) to the environment and the NMs can be recycled at the end of life.
- ***Pillar 2- safer use of products:*** This consists of evaluating the risks during all uses throughout the product lifecycle to optimize defined acceptable uses. Building on the first SbD pillar, when a product has been made as safe as possible, this second pillar will facilitate an evaluation and determine any potential restrictions on the use of a specific NEP.
- ***Pillar 3- safer industrial production:*** This pillar aims to enable better control on the industrial processes along the production chain. The aim is to design processes that eliminate/reduce the release of NMs to the workplace and outdoor environment, do not use hazardous chemicals, reduce NM-waste, do not pose hazard concerns (e.g., explosion), and optimize energy consumption.

3. Factors contributing to risks

3.1 NMs properties

The OECD recently published a report (OECD, 2019) that provides information regarding the physico-chemical parameters that drive risks and on which SbD approaches could be applied. The framework is divided in three phases, 1: “Nanomaterial Identification and Information Gathering”, 2: “Physico-chemical Properties for Exposure and Fate Assessment” and 3: “Physico-chemical Properties for Hazard Assessment”. Results from this report can be used for SbD purposes. An example is presented in Table 2 (extracted from the OECD report), describing different potential toxicity mechanisms and the relevant routes of exposure. This allows the prioritization of the physico-chemical parameters that are required for initiating such mechanisms. As an example, a fiber-like toxicity mechanism is a concern for inhalation exposure with the aspect ratio being one of the parameters initiating the mechanism. The mechanism's intensity is expected to be driven by the flexural rigidity, dissolution rate in lung fluid, and the surface area parameters.

Table 2. Decision Framework for physico-chemical parameters for Exposure and Fate Assessment extracted from the OECD report (OECD, 2019).

Mechanism of Concern	Relevant exposure route	Potential Initiating Physico-Chemical Properties	Modifying Physico-Chemical Properties
Fiber-like Toxicity	Inhalation	Aspect Ratio Length	Flexural rigidity Dissolution rate in lung fluid Surface Area
Surface Reactivity	All	Surface Chemistry Surface Layer thickness	Surface Area Surface Wettability Surface Charge
Reactive Oxygen Species Generation	All	Surface & Chemical Composition Surface defect sites	Surface Area Adsorption from solution Passivation propensity Surface defect density
Interference with Intracellular Redox processes	All but dermal	Conduction Band Energy level	Particle Surface Structure and Composition Fermi Levels Homo-Lumo Levels of interacting biomolecules Adsorbed molecules (e.g., protein corona)
Photocatalytic Activity	Environmental	UV-Visible Light Adsorption	Band Gap Crystallinity Recombination Rate Surface Area Adsorbed Molecules Adhesion to Impacted Organisms
Trojan Horse Phenomena	All	Surface Chemistry / Affinity	Surface Area Surface Ionisation/Charge Adsorbed molecules Hydrophobicity
Affinity to Aquatic and Terrestrial Organisms	Environmental	Surface Affinity	Hamaker Constant Surface Charge Hydrophobicity Adsorbed Molecules Shape Size Porosity
Soluble Compound Release	All	Chemical/Structural Composition	Surface Area Dissolution Rate Agglomeration State Stability of coating

Despite no quantitative thresholds being provided, this is a good summary and guidance for potential strategies that could be considered for SbD purposes. Some quantitative and/or threshold data for some NMs properties associated with a route of exposure can be found in the literature, but this task is highly challenging and threshold values do not have a real consensus. The GRACIOUS¹⁰ project aims to generate these thresholds for some properties of NMs associated with hazard and exposure concerns. However, the main goal of GRACIOUS is to generate a highly innovative science-based framework to enable grouping, read-across and classification of nanomaterials/nanoforms (NFs). Furthermore, in other projects such as SAbYNA, more emphasis was placed on generating a Guidance SbD platform to guide users on the implementation of the SbD concept in their innovation process as early as possible. Some of the findings after the analysis of existing strategies for SbD (reported in literature) and the key physico-chemical parameters targeted, pointed out that factors governing dissolution rate and surface-related properties appear to be of primary interest.

3.2 Nano-enabled product design

For most applications, NMs are incorporated in matrices to generate the final commercial NEPs. It has been shown that manufacturing processes leading to NEPs, but also uses and applications of NEPs drive potential release/exposure of NMs (Ruggiero *et al.*, 2019; Wohlleben *et al.*, 2016; Duncan, 2015). During the product life cycle, different aging factors may induce NMs release from the NEP. The aging factor can be purely physical (abrasion, drilling), chemical (landfilling) or a combination of mechanical and chemical stresses. For example, during dermal contact, the hand rubbing induces a smooth and low energy mechanical stress and the skin sweat can induce chemical stress on nano-enabled textiles leading to potential NM releases (Kuhlbusch *et al.*, 2011; Mackevica *et al.*, 2016; Golanski *et al.*, 2011; Caballero-Guzman & Nowack, 2016; Wohlleben *et al.*, 2014). The physico-chemical state of the matrix (solid, liquid, aerosol) is one of the main factors affecting the release of NFs, for example, for liquid and aerosol NEP, 100 % of NMs included is expected to be released during the product use (i.e., considering 100 % of product use) (Foss Hansen *et al.*, 2007). NMs incorporated in sunscreens will be released either in the swimming area or in wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). In the case of solid matrices, the location of the NMs in the product matrix is one of the main drivers for NMs release, e.g., NMs present as a coating are more likely to be released than NMs embedded in the full body of the matrices (Duncan & Pillai, 2015). Another parameter to consider is the affinity of the NMs and the product matrix, as covalently bond NMs show lower release than electrostatically bond NMs (i.e. NMs bond to the textile fiber during washing). The understanding of NMs release mechanism during the NEP life cycle is key but can be rather complex as presented in Figure 3.

¹⁰ <https://www.h2020gracious.eu/>

Figure 3. Schematic showing some potential ENM release pathways from polymer nanocomposite materials due to mechanical degradation or chemical decomposition of the host material extracted from Duncan & Pillai (2015).

In the GRACIOUS project, for the purpose of grouping and to support some grouping exposure based-hypothesis, different processes that could lead to release of NM (e.g., food contact, weathering, abrasion, incineration, landfilling) were considered as well as specific properties (e.g. NEP matrix degradability, NMs properties, NMs location, or binding type in the NEP matrix) to group NEP based on their release rate and release form. Each process as described below is linked to a route of exposure and the corresponding human or environmental compartments.

3.3 Safe nano-process

Focusing on occupational settings, the SbD concept was also related to the safe design of the working process. It is well known that workers can be exposed to NMs generated from working activities and to background aerosols. The NMs emitted by industrial activities and NMs handling may be engineered and used as input/output in the manufacturing process, or non-engineered and/or formed unintentionally as a result of a given industrial activity (Salmatonidis *et al.*, 2019). To avoid possible NM emission, the designer can act on specific process parameters (e.g. energy involved, temperature, speed) and if this is not possible, the designer can implement efficient exposure mitigation strategies.

The European Council (Directive 98/24/EC 70) recommends the elimination or isolation of sources as methods to minimize exposures to hazardous substances in workplaces. If these measures are not applicable, engineering controls should be applied (e.g. dilution and local exhaust ventilation).

3.4 Safe NM by Production Control

SbD methods generate NMs which are safer when produced in perfectly controlled lab-scale conditions. In large-scale industrial production, however, manufactured NMs may not meet the SbD specifications, due to different and varying operating conditions, the high variability of raw materials, and faults, and shortcomings in the production processes. An additional SbD level, named Safe by Process Control (SbPC) stage, is being investigated in the recently funded SABYDOMA¹¹ H2020 project, to ensure that NM production meets the desired safety specifications. The method is largely based on the availability of on-line sensors like HISENTS, which can inform us in real-time about the condition of the produced NMs in terms of safety specifications and on the development of dynamical predictive models that link production line variables with the outcomes of the advanced online automated high-throughput screening methods and the ToxScore technology. A Model Predictive Controller (MPC) is designed next, which minimizes the error value between the desired set-point(s) and the measured, controlled variable(s). Error minimisation is performed by formulating and solving, in real-time, a mathematical optimisation problem, where the dynamic model plays the role of the predictor. MPC is a multivariable control method, able to simultaneously handle more than one control objective, which is of particular importance on the industrial scale, where we need to simultaneously control toxicity, functionality, and efficiency. Another key advantage of MPC is its ability to incorporate several types of constraints into the formulation of optimisation problems and to enforce physicochemical properties to be within acceptable limits that guarantee that NM production meets the desired functionality requirements.

¹¹ <https://www.sabydoma.eu/>

4. Tools available through the NanoCommons infrastructure to support the SbD concept

Various predictive models have been developed, implemented, and published through the NanoCommons infrastructure, which can support the safer product design concept. The user can predict how changes in functional properties of NMs may affect their toxicity and select the values of these parameters allowing to reduce their adverse effects. Additionally, the NanoCommons RA workflow, developed in the context of WP6, supports the safer process design concept by providing an integrated simulation environment, where various process parameters (e.g. temperature, humidity) and risk mitigation measures can be tested for minimising exposures to hazardous substances in manufacturing workplaces. This section presents briefly the various tools and gives emphasis on specific case studies that showcase how the tools can support the SbD concept:

1. Tools to retrieve and compile information from databases for further use in SbD tools.
2. Tools for grouping of NMs
3. Safer Product Design using predictive models available through the Jaqpot and Enalos platforms. Two specific case studies are presented in detail.
4. Safer Process Design using the integrated NanoCommons RA workflow presented in D6.1 and D6.3. A complete case study is presented with the quantification of SbD mitigation measures.

4.1 Extract information for SbD from the NanoCommons Knowledge base

Access to experimental and computational data is crucial for feeding the predictive models and the computational workflows that are presented later in this section. The NanoCommons data management system, called NanoCommons Knowledge Base (KB), is a central source of information and has been developed around appropriate ontological concepts in partnership with other major current and completed nanosafety projects.

Through the NanoCommons Knowledge Base the user can retrieve experimental, modeling and simulation datasets from nanosafety projects. The user can search for relevant data and transform it to produce their own sub-dataset and use it as input to specific SbD tools.

To transform the particular datasets in a ready to modeling format, a KNIME node has been developed within the NanoCommons project, to give access to the publicly available datasets within the NanoCommons Knowledge Base through Enalos APIs (Varsou *et al.*, 2018).

With the aid of Enalos APIs (Varsou *et al.*, 2018; Afantitis *et al.*, 2020) and nodes (through a server-client architecture), the user can automate common procedures that greatly facilitate the rapid workflow prototyping within KNIME. The Enalos NanoCommons KB node can be very useful in accessing and analyzing different toxicity and physicochemical datasets. Enalos+ KNIME nodes and Enalos APIs allow physicochemical characterization, toxicological and omics data (such as DLS, Zeta potential, TEM size, % of viable cells, IC50, gene expression data) to be accessed in a data matrix format for further analysis directly within the KNIME analytics platform, as shown in Figure 4.

Enalos NanoCommons Knowledgebase

This KNIME nodes give access to NanoCommons Knowledgebase nanomaterials datasets through Enalos APIs.

Physicochemical, toxicological and omics characterisation data such as DLS, Zeta, TEM size % of viable cells, IC50, gene expression data etc can be downloaded in a data matrix format for further analysis with in the KNIME analytics platform.

Ports

Output Ports	
0	Data matrix format of Physchem or Toxicity Data

This node is contained in *Node extension for KNIME Workbench* provided by *NanoCommons Project*.

Figure 4. Enalos NanoCommons KB KNIME node.

A brief demonstration of the use of the Enalos NanoCommons Knowledge Base node is presented in the form of an example workflow for data extraction and manipulation shown in Figure 5. It is highlighted that data extraction can be achieved in just a few steps and with minimum time required.

Figure 5. A simple KNIME workflow for data extraction from NanoCommons KB and filtering. Available also as a Transnational Access (TA) application¹².

With the aid of predefined automated steps, the user can extract the datasets of interest, curate and transform them in a data matrix format ready for further nanoinformatics and predictive modeling analysis (Table 3).

Table 3. Data extracted through Enalos + nodes curated and ready for further computational analysis.

Row ID	Measurement	Table Cell Count	Value	D_Mol	D_Mol	D_Cell	D_Mol	D_Lipid	D_Mol	D_Total	D_Fract	D_Cyts	S_Particle	S_Tox Inf.	S_Tox Br
Row 0_Row 0	TC000000000000197	1.079	0.488	-0.473	-0.503	-0.568	-0.464	0.412	-0.652	-0.181	-0.369	NP00192	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 1_Row 4	TC000000000000198	-0.398	0.02	-0.581	0.075	-0.326	0.436	-0.033	-1.397	0.557	-0.87	NP00205	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 2_Row 8	TC000000000000199	-1.133	-0.309	-0.956	-0.774	-1.26	-0.302	0.603	-0.752	0.476	-1.389	NP00209	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 3_Row 13	TC000000000000200	-0.652	0.526	0.582	0.246	0.406	-0.846	0.676	-0.598	0.281	-0.791	NP00375	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 4_Row 2	TC000000000000201	-0.184	0.27	0.05	-0.308	-0.225	-0.529	-0.035	-0.844	0.623	-0.824	NP00214	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 4_Row 3	TC000000000000201	-0.184	0.27	0.05	-0.308	-0.225	-0.529	-0.035	-0.844	0.623	-0.824	NP00214	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 5_Row 7	TC000000000000202	-0.64	0.329	0.202	-0.539	-0.775	-0.327	0.851	-0.464	-0.328	-0.79	NP00298	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 6_Row 11	TC000000000000203	-0.369	0.131	-0.176	0.763	-0.913	-0.645	0.758	-1.133	-0.347	-0.996	NP00283	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 6_Row 12	TC000000000000203	-0.769	0.131	-0.176	0.763	-0.913	-0.645	0.758	-1.133	-0.347	-0.996	NP00283	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 7_Row 2	TC000000000000204	-0.469	-0.223	0.123	0.275	0.3	-0.069	-0.658	-0.02	0.807	-0.582	NP00214	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 7_Row 3	TC000000000000204	-0.469	-0.223	0.123	0.275	0.3	-0.069	-0.658	-0.02	0.807	-0.582	NP00214	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 7_Row 6	TC000000000000205	-0.823	0.094	-0.032	0.01	-0.374	-0.138	1.004	-0.692	-0.596	-0.731	NP00257	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 8_Row 11	TC000000000000206	-0.366	0.428	0.139	-0.887	-0.758	0.375	1.348	0.28	-0.663	-0.908	NP00283	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 8_Row 12	TC000000000000206	-0.366	0.428	0.139	-0.887	-0.758	0.375	1.348	0.28	-0.663	-0.908	NP00283	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 10_Row 1	TC000000000000207	0.679	0.26	0.309	-0.863	-0.031	-0.405	0.751	-0.779	-0.28	-0.996	NP00192	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 11_Row 5	TC000000000000208	-0.288	-0.052	-0.185	-0.223	-0.002	-0.244	0.321	-0.643	-0.088	-0.407	NP00295	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 12_Row 10	TC000000000000209	-0.182	-0.138	1.067	0.065	1.361	-0.358	1.064	-1.286	0.376	-0.426	NP00282	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 13_Row 9	TC000000000000210	-0.928	0.33	-0.682	-1.158	-1.201	-0.468	0.807	-0.133	-0.258	-0.812	NP00260	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 14_Row 17	TC000000000000211	0.191	-0.208	-0.304	-1.388	-0.885	-0.812	1.117	-0.29	-0.765	-0.943	NP00489	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 15_Row 21	TC000000000000212	0.76	0.644	0.177	0.467	-0.332	-0.538	0.565	-0.637	-0.111	-1.084	NP00489	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 16_Row 25	TC000000000000213	-1.174	0.586	-0.893	-1.585	-0.985	-0.736	0.426	-0.677	-0.105	-1.095	NP00487	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 17_Row 28	TC000000000000214	-0.342	-0.083	-0.383	-1.494	-0.663	-0.649	1.579	-0.796	-0.765	-1.323	NP00488	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 18_Row 20	TC000000000000215	-1.085	1.129	0.348	-0.336	-0.468	-0.753	0.263	-0.924	0.468	-1.096	NP00492	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 19_Row 24	TC000000000000216	-0.818	0.328	-0.749	-1.354	-1.119	-0.213	0.749	-0.879	0.14	-1.877	NP00496	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 20_Row 15	TC000000000000217	-0.176	0.129	0.061	-1.094	-1.226	-0.518	1.004	-0.511	0.03	-1.873	NP00487	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 21_Row 19	TC000000000000218	-1.306	0.426	-1.078	0.013	-1.045	-0.056	0.446	-1.126	-0.105	-0.617	NP00481	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 22_Row 23	TC000000000000219	-1.833	1.337	-0.084	0.091	-0.875	-0.908	1.452	-0.663	0.09	-1.976	NP00491	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 23_Row 14	TC000000000000220	-0.368	-0.596	-0.56	-0.408	-0.299	0.361	0.858	0.363	-0.387	-1.295	NP00486	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 24_Row 18	TC000000000000221	-1.185	0.059	-0.561	0.975	-0.826	0.332	1.603	-0.845	-0.401	-1.783	NP00490	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 25_Row 22	TC000000000000222	-0.591	0.308	-0.021	-0.026	-0.611	-0.75	0.6	-0.591	0.455	-2.047	NP00494	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 26_Row 10	TC000000000000223	-0.083	0.377	0.028	-0.389	-1.235	0.203	1.638	-0.248	-1.473	0.994	NP00282	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 27_Row 0	TC000000000000224	-0.82	0.249	-0.683	-1.191	-0.608	0.127	0.911	-0.478	-0.946	0.102	NP00192	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 28_Row 4	TC000000000000225	-0.448	0.224	-0.109	-0.221	-0.282	0.626	1.192	-0.274	-1.32	0.39	NP00281	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 29_Row 8	TC000000000000226	-1.218	-0.132	-1.429	-1.044	-1.041	0.231	0.828	-0.568	-0.088	-0.628	NP00199	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 30_Row 13	TC000000000000227	0.517	0.477	-0.668	-0.766	-0.193	-0.48	0.682	-0.08	-0.75	0.5	NP00375	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 31_Row 1	TC000000000000228	-0.365	0.175	-0.158	0.798	0.275	0.958	0.896	0.405	-0.722	-0.289	NP00214	HeptalG	24.0 h	
Row 31_Row 3	TC000000000000228	-0.365	0.175	-0.158	0.798	0.275	0.958	0.896	0.405	-0.722	-0.289	NP00214	HeptalG	24.0 h	

¹² <https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/services/26/nanocommons-knowledgebase-access-within-knime-through-enalos-apis/>

4.2 NMs grouping

As extensively detailed in the NanoCommons deliverable 6.2 “AOP-based grouping of NMs”, the grouping is extremely important to assess if a NM is different from another and could be exploited for SbD purposes when aiming at NMs substitution (Drew *et al.*, 2017; Oomen *et al.*, 2015; Lynch *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, the similarity concept was also exploited by the European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals (ECETOC) to develop a new tool to support the industry in the registration of sets of nanoforms, as well as regulators in the evaluation of these registration dossiers. Table 4 summarizes the tiered approach of the ECETOC NanoApp¹³.

Table 4. Tiered approach of the ECETOC NanoApp extracted from Janer *et al.* (2020).

Properties considered in both Tier 1 and Tier 2	Additional data required in Tier 2	Additional data optional in Tier 3 ^a
Main constituents (CAS Number, relative content)	Reactivity, environmental dissolution, physiological dissolution AND <i>in vitro</i> toxicity	
Crystallinity (crystalline forms, relative content)	Literature data on comparative toxicity OR reactivity, environmental dissolution and physiological dissolution.	
Impurities/non-covalently bound additives (relative content)	Environmental dissolution, physiological dissolution, reactivity, <i>in vitro</i> toxicity, AND environmental dispersion stability	
Covalently bound surface treatments (CAS Number, relative content, CLP)	Environmental dissolution, physiological dissolution, AND reactivity. AND <i>in vitro</i> toxicity if surface treatments are not of identical chemistry.	
CLP based in chemical composition		
Particle size distribution (d50 and d90)	Environmental dissolution, physiological dissolution, reactivity, <i>in vitro</i> toxicity, AND environmental dispersion stability	<i>In vivo</i> toxicity and biokinetics
Shape category, aspect ratio, assembly structure, and length (d90, only for elongated NFs)	<i>In vitro</i> toxicity	
Mass specific surface area	Environmental dissolution, physiological dissolution, reactivity, <i>in vitro</i> toxicity, AND environmental dispersion stability	
Production process (in relation to environmental dispersion stability)	Environmental dispersion stability and dustiness	

^aA Tier 3 based on an *in vivo* study is only optionally presented, as a temporary solution, for special cases in which existing *in vitro* studies do not provide reliable predictions. As an alternative to performing such *in vivo* study, the sets can also be justified based on preselection of the worst-case nanoform in the set for further regulatory testing (*cf.* chapter 8).

4.3 Safer Product Design using predictive models through Jaqpot and Enalos

QSAR models are mathematical models derived from the algorithmic analysis of available experimental activity training data, which are able to predict the unknown activities of other compounds, directly from structural characteristics (called “descriptors”). An in-depth review of NanoCommons involvement in nanoQSAR modelling has been presented in D5.4. Under the NanoCommons project, a series of nanoQSAR models have been developed and, along with literature models, have been exposed as ready-to-use web services on the Jaqpot and Enalos modelling environments. Table 5 presents the list of available nanoQSAR models on Jaqpot. This list is expected to expand further through the upcoming scheduled Transnational Access (TA) projects.

Table 5. Available nanoQSAR web services uploaded into the Jaqpot modelling environment

Model Description	Model Input	Model Endpoint
Naive Bayes model for predicting cytotoxicity of metal oxide NMs	Oxidation number, ionic potential, surface reducibility, reduction potential	Cytotoxicity of various organisms as log (EC50)

¹³ <https://www.ecetoc.org/tools/nanoapp/>

Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting pEC50 in metal oxide NMs	Periodic table-based descriptors	Cytotoxicity of E.Coli measured as pEC50
Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting photo-induced toxicity of metal oxide NMs (light)	Molar heat capacity, average of the alpha and beta LUMO energies	Cytotoxicity of E.Coli measured as log(EC50)
Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting photo-induced toxicity of metal oxide NMs (dark)	Absolute electronegativity of the metal atom, absolute electronegativity of the metal oxide	Cytotoxicity of E.Coli measured as log(EC50)
Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting the toxicity of aggregated zero valent copper NMs	pH, temperature, Aeration rate, concentration of NMs, concentration of bacteria	Cytotoxicity of E.Coli measured as percentage of dead E. Coli population
Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting LDH after ZnO NMs Cellular Exposures	Size in water, Concentration, Zeta Potential	Cytotoxicity - membrane damage measured as lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release [units/L]
Linear model for predicting solubility of C60 fullerenes in various solvents	Molecular multiple path count of order 03, Broto-Mreau autocorrelation of a topological structure-lag 1/weighted by atomic masses, Eigenvalue sum from polarizability weighted distance matrix, 3D-MORSE-signal 23/weighted by atomic sanderson electronegativities, autocorrelation of lag 1/weighted by atomic masses	Solubility in organic solvents measured as logarithmic values of molar fractions log(S)
Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting cytotoxicity in metal oxide NMs	Polarization force parameter, enthalpy of formation of a gaseous cation having the same oxidation state as that in the metal oxide structure.	Cytotoxicity of E.Coli measured as log(1/EC50)
Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting LDH of TiO2 NMs	Engineered size, size in water size in PBS, concentration, zeta potential	Cytotoxicity - membrane damage measured as lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release

		[units/L]
Stepwise multiple linear regression model for predicting LDH of TiO ₂ NMs	Size in water, concentration, zeta potential	Cytotoxicity - membrane damage measured as lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) release [units/L]
Multiple linear regression model for predicting adsorption coefficient in carbon based NMs	Lipophilicity interaction, hydrogen bond basicity, hydrogen bond acidity, dipolarity/polarizability, lone-pair electrons	logarithm of adsorption coefficient
Neural network model for predicting solubility of C ₆₀ fullerenes in various solvents	Molecular multiple path count of order 03, Broto-Mrean autocorrelation of a topological structure-lag 1/weighted by atomic masses, Eigenvalue sum from polarizability weighted distance matrix, 3D-MORSE-signal 23/weighted by atomic sanderson electronegativities, autocorrelation of lag 1/weighted by atomic masses	Solubility in organic solvents measured as logarithmic values of molar fractions log(S)

NanoQSARs can be utilized in a SbD strategy: Given a toxicity related endpoint, nanoQSAR models can link the physicochemical characteristics of a NM to the response. Therefore, NM properties can be designed *in silico* prior to manufacturing for ensuring that the material has the desired behavior. Use of nanoQSARs in a repetitive manner can be used to control the characteristics of the NM to achieve non-toxic responses. The use of nanoQSAR for supporting the safer product design concept (NanoREG2 Pillar 1) is illustrated through case studies reported in the following sections.

4.3.1 Design of MWCNTs with desired toxicity and protein binding properties

The models are available for public use and verification through the Enalos Cloud platform¹⁴ and can be used to observe the effects of the different inputs (decorating molecule structures) on the prediction of CA binding to the MWCNTs and the toxicity of the resultant decorated-MWCNTs. Through this platform the need to reduce the amount of time and cost spent in experimental testing can be addressed, using *in silico* tools for safe-by-design that produce accurate predictions for drug discovery and risk assessment of small molecules and NMs. The MWCNTs decorators and the surface area of the decorator is also their “contact area” with the biological environment, while the surface electrostatic status influences the MWCNT behavior in the exposed environment. For example, it is reported in the literature (Arai & Norde, 1990; Peng *et al.*, 2005) that electrostatic interactions directly

¹⁴ <http://enalos.insilicotox.com/CNT/>

induce the adsorption of proteins onto NMs, thus the surface charge of the MWCNTs, which is conferred by the decorating ligands, is an important factor, greatly related to the CA binding endpoint. The main target of the proposed model was to offer a computational tool that will simplify the design and screening of novel MWCNTs by allowing prediction of the CA binding and cellular toxicity based only on the chemical structure of the surface decoration molecule, as part of a SbD strategy that would allow elimination of potentially toxic modifications at the design stage. Making the tool available online with a user friendly interface, enhances its utility as an aid for the decision making of interested research, industry and regulatory groups. The user-friendly web service facilitates the computer-aided design of novel MWCNTs by the interested users (computational experts or not); the Enalos Cloud platform can be easily accessed and can be directly explored by anyone interested in MWCNTs design to optimize functionality and safety (i.e. safe-by-design), without any need for prior programming skills. The user-friendly interface can be seen below in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Enalos Nanoinformatics Cloud platform user-friendly interface. Users can simply draw the chemical structure of the decorating ligand, or upload a Spatial Data File (SDF) containing the molecular structure(s) of interest.

During a SbD process, different data sets with decorators of interest can be imported, and their effects on the biological and toxicological behaviour of the resulting decorated MWCNTs can be studied. More particularly the user can insert one or several structures of compounds being considered as potential decorating molecules for MWCNTs and get, within seconds, the prediction of the CA binding and their toxicity profile, along with a warning on the reliability of the predictions based on the models' domain of applicability limits. The user has three different options for providing the structures of the compounds to be screened: (i) by drawing the chemical structure of interest, (ii) by entering the SMILES notation of the compounds in the appropriate field or (iii) by uploading an .sdf file with a batch of compounds (Figure 4).

The developed models can be used under a virtual screening framework for the development of novel, plus safe, decorated MWCNTs. Initially, we tried to improve the profiles of MWCNT samples identified in the initial dataset as having unsatisfactory toxicity and high protein binding properties (toxic and a

CA binder sample). We have to underline at this point that, depending on the nature of the specific proteins that bind, protein binding can increase a NMs engagement with specific cellular receptors thus enhancing uptake, or can increase or reduce the susceptibility to phagocytosis (depending on whether the corona presents opsonizing or disopsonising proteins) or can create cryptic epitopes in cellular signaling proteins causing toxic responses. We also performed a sensitivity analysis to explore the toxicity and the protein binding limits of the samples, by inserting, deleting or modifying substituents at different positions of the decorators.

To begin with, we selected three MWCNT samples with unsatisfactory toxicity and CA protein binding responses and through a similarity search in the PubChem database we proposed a group of potential surface modifying compounds that could lead to samples with the desired (low) toxicity and (low) protein binding levels. Therefore, we selected the AMOO4AC002, the AMOO7AC002 and the AMOO8AC002 samples which are toxic and bind CA from the initial dataset. For their substituents, as presented in Figure 8 using the Enalos+ PubChem Similarity and the Main PubChem KNIME nodes, we searched the whole PubChem repository for similar substituents to the reference substituents of the initial samples. Tanimoto similarity measure was selected as 98% for both substituents R1 and R2.

After filtering the duplicate generated substituent SMILES, we created a list of 942 candidate surface modifiers by combining the different substituents in positions R1 and R2 with the core molecule. We uploaded an .sdf file including these structures to the web-service, and within seconds we acquired the predictions for their CA binding and toxicity profiles, as well as the reliability of these predictions according to the APD limits. According to our initial plan, we were only interested in MWCNTs with reduced toxicity and low protein binding, thus from the generated predictions we focused only on non-toxic and CA non-binder results. From these, we excluded the samples with unreliable outcomes and 32 MWCNT samples with desired properties remained. In a final step, we checked if the valence on the atoms of the structure is correct in KNIME, using the Valence Checker node. The valence was correct for the structures therefore they can be considered feasible.

To test the sensitivity of the proposed method to vary the decorator compounds, we slightly altered (Tanimoto similarity over 91%) the decorator's structure of a sample with desired properties from the initial dataset. Sample AMOO3AC005(1) is a non-toxic CA non-binder that was used as the input structure for extracting similar compounds in the way described previously. After filtering the duplicate generated SMILES, 26 compounds remained, to be tested in the dedicated CNT web service we have developed as described above. From the produced predictions we focused only on the 13 reliable ones, according to the calculated applicability domain. Finally, in order to be consistent with the initial structure of the MWCNTs as depicted in Figure 7 we excluded the compounds that did not meet its main components; *i.e.*, the structure of the linker and the substituent base. The selected altered decorators are also presented in Figure 7.

Initial decorators

AMO04AC002

AMO07AC002

AMO08AC002

Potential decorators

C1=CC(=CC=C1)C(OC2=CC=C(C=C2)CC(C(NCCCCOC(=O)C1=CC=CC=C1)=O)NC1=CC=C(C=C1)C=O)=O

C1=CC(=CC=C1)C(OC2=CC=C(C=C2)CC(C(NCC=CC=CC=CCO(C=O)C1=CC=CC=C1)=O)NC1=CC=C(C=C1)C=O)=O

C1=CC(=CC=C1)C(OC2=CC=C(C=C2)CC(C(NCOCCCCCOC(=O)C1=CC=CC=C1)=O)NC1=CC=C(C=C1)C=O)=O

Figure 7. Altered decorators according to an initial one with desired properties, for sensitivity analysis.

4.3.2 MS3bD: Design of NMs with desired ζ -potential properties assisted by read-across

A new predictive model for the prediction of ζ -potential of NMs in water has been developed within NanoCommons, which is directly applicable to SbD workflows and strategies. The model was developed with the help of the Isalos Analytics Platform and is titled Molecular, Size and Surface based Safe by Design (MScubed, MS³bD) Zeta Potential predictive model (Papadiamantis *et al.*, under revision). The model, complemented with a user-friendly GUI, is available as a webservice through the NanoCommons instance at the Enalos Cloud Platform¹⁵, while being integrated at the

¹⁵ <http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/nanocommons/mszeta/>

NanoCommons KB. The benefit of the MS³bD predictive model is that it is based on a combination of molecular and physicochemical NMs characteristics. These include:

- Physicochemical: coating type and core NM size (as measured with TEM or STEM)
- Molecular: core metal ionic radius, sum of core metal electronegativity divided by the number of oxygens present and the absolute (or Mulliken) electronegativity.

These descriptors are directly related with the mechanisms regulating the surface charge of the core NM and at the same time the observed ζ -potential for NMs. The latter is strongly related to the type of coating, as it can substantially modify (i.e. mask the core NM surface charge) the ζ -potential observed during respective experimental measurements. The parameters used to predict the ζ -potential do not require any experimental measurements, as the molecular descriptors can be calculated or retrieved from relevant databases and users can experiment with the coatings available within the tool and different sizes to reach the desired ζ -potential values.

For example, a user would like to calculate the observed ζ -potential for an uncoated TiO₂ NM with a core size of 20 nm and how this changes if different coating types are applied as shown in Figure 8. In this case, the user inputs the molecular properties for TiO₂ and keeps the core size stable, while changing the coating type (if any, line 1 is for the uncoated NM). The results are presented in Figure 9, where the user can see the respective changes to ζ -potential due to the coating. The user can see the NMs in which the prediction was based (as can be seen in Figure X the majority are other TiO₂ NMs). The user can also see whether the prediction is considered reliable or not, based on the comparison of the calculated domain of applicability for the model with the value calculated for the entire model.

MS³bD Zeta Potential Predictive Model

Note Please that the ζ -potential predictive model has been developed assuming that the dispersion medium is water and as such the dispersion medium pH is 7 and the theoretical ionic strength is 10⁻⁶-6.998 mol/L. Direct usage for different conditions will result in unreliable measurements.

[User Guide](#)

Nanomaterial type	Coating	Core diameter (TEM-STEM)	Metal ionic radius	$\Sigma \chi_n O$	Absolute electronegativity
TiO ₂	uncoated	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	4% (w/v) each of polyoxyethy	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	sulfate & PVP capped	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	Tannic acid / sodium citrate	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	HMTA	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	PEG 1500	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	Ethylenediamine	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	PVP	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	AA4040	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	D540	20	67	0.77	5.77
TiO ₂	sodium citrate	20	67	0.77	5.77

Figure 8. Calculation of ζ -potential prediction for a TiO₂ NM with a core size of 20 nm and different coatings using the MS³bD tool.

This particular model uses the oxidation number (Z), ionic potential (IP), surface reducibility (SR) and redox reactivity (RR) of a metal oxide NM in order to predict its cytotoxicity. Specifically, $\log(\text{EC}_{50})$ values have been mapped to very low toxicity (VLT), low toxicity (LT), high toxicity (HT) and very high toxicity (VHT). For a NM with $Z \leq 2$, $\text{IP} \leq 3$, non reducible SR and non active RR, the final output is very high toxicity (Figures 13 and 14). In order to reduce the toxic response, a series of changes in the physicochemical properties of the NM were tested. After trying a few combinations of parameters on the QSAR model using a trial and error approach, the design of a new metal oxide is proposed, with increased oxidation number ($Z = 3$) and ionic potential ($\text{IP} > 5$), for which a very low toxicity value is obtained (Figure 15).

The screenshot shows the Jaqpot web application interface. The top navigation bar includes the Jaqpot logo, a search bar, and user notification icons. The main content area is divided into four tabs: Overview, Features, Predict / Validate (active), and Discussion. On the left, a sidebar displays model information for a Naive Bayes model. The main area contains a 'Choose method' dropdown set to 'Predict', an 'Upload dataset' section with up/down arrows, and an 'Input values for the independent features' section. This section includes a 'Sort' button and four input boxes: Oxidation Number Z (value: 1), Ionic Potential IP (value: 1), Redox Reactivity RR (value: 2), and Surface Reducibility SR (value: 3). Each box also contains a legend for its values. A 'Start' button is located at the bottom right of the input section.

Figure 13. Initial input of the case study: a NM with For a NM with $Z \leq 2$, $I \leq 3$, non-reducible SR and non-active RR is tested in silico for its toxicity.

The screenshot shows the Jaqpot web interface. The navigation bar includes a menu icon, the Jaqpot logo, a search bar, and user profile icons. The main content area is divided into four tabs: Overview, Features, Predict / Validate, and Discussion. The Predict / Validate tab is active, showing a prediction result for a Naive Bayes model. The model title is "Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles". The owner is Haralambos Sarimveis. The description is "Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles using fundamental physical-chemical parameters". The prediction result is displayed in a table with the following data:

Id	Redox Reactivity RR	Class of toxicity	Oxidation Number Z	Surface Reducibility SR	Ionic Potential IP
0	2	VHT	1	3	1

Below the table, there are buttons for "Download" and "Archive". The interface also shows a "View predicted value only" button and a "Task Completed Successfully" message.

Figure 14. Toxicity results for a NM with For a NM with $Z \leq 2$, $IP \leq 3$, non-reducible SR and non-active RR. The naive bayes model predicts that a NM with these properties has a very high toxicity.

The screenshot shows the Jaqpot web interface. The top navigation bar includes the Jaqpot logo, a search bar, and user profile icons. The main content area is divided into four tabs: Overview, Features, Predict / Validate (active), and Discussion. On the left sidebar, a model card is displayed with the following information:

- MODEL**
- Title:** Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles
- Owner:** Haralambos Sarimveis
- Description:** Naive Bayes model for the prediction of cytotoxicity of metal oxide nanoparticles using fundamental physical-chemical parameters

The main content area shows a progress log for the prediction process:

- Searching dataset...
- Dataset has been retrieved.
- Starting Prediction...
- Prediction completed successfully.
- Dataset was built successfully.
- Now saving to database...
- Task Completed Successfully.

A blue checkmark icon indicates successful completion. Below the log is a button labeled "View predicted value only". A table displays the prediction results:

Id	Redox Reactivity RR	Class of toxicity	Oxidation Number Z	Surface Reducibility SR	Ionic Potential IP
0	2	VLT	3	3	3

At the bottom of the table, it shows "Items per page: 30" and "1 - 1 of 1". There are also "Download" and "Archive" buttons at the bottom left, and a pink circular icon at the bottom right.

Figure 15. Toxicity results for a NM with For a NM with $Z = 3$, $IP > 5$, non-reducible SR and non-active RR. The naive bayes model predicts that a NM with these properties has a very low toxicity.

4.4 Implementation of SbD strategy in the NanoCommons RA framework

4.4.1 Tools description

Within WP6, NanoCommons has proposed a novel risk assessment workflow that introduces the concepts of personalised RA and also RA at the level of AOP, i.e. estimating the likelihood of triggering particular AOPs. This concept requires the scientific interconnection of various modelling approaches, including exposure, biokinetics and omics analysis methodologies. In D6.3 we have demonstrated that this integration is not only scientifically, but also technically feasible. The state-of-the-art technologies that are used for developing the NanoCommons computational services allow the seamless integration of the tools and the creation of novel computational workflows.

A limitation in the implementation of the decision support integrated RA workflow was lack of experimental data that restricted the domain on which this risk assessment concept can be applied. Gene expression data were only available for mice and this limitation drove the complete case study. However, the different tools comprising the workflow and the complete application can be easily adjusted to other case studies, provided that the required experimental data are available.

4.4.2 Description of the risk assessment workflow

In Deliverable D6.1 we described the novel NanoCommons RA workflow that the user can follow to define an exposure scenario and perform exposure, hazard and finally RA (Figure 12). The first step for creating exposure scenarios is to gather the data regarding the ENM of interest. In particular, its physicochemical properties, and detailed information related to the process (during which exposure may occur), the duration of the exposure, the exposed populations (e.g., humans, environmental specie(s) and organism(s)) as well as ecological data -if available- are incorporated into each scenario. The checklist provided in Deliverable D6.1 is valuable in organizing the data collection process. When both the exposure level and the relevant hazard reference point are available, the calculation of the risk characterisation ratio (RCR) is direct. If this is not the case, the NanoCommons RA workflow suggests many alternative modelling tools and approaches (from those integrated into the NanoCommons toolbox) for estimating the exposure levels and predicting the hazard reference points (RPs), as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Flowchart of the NanoCommons nanoinformatics-based RA workflow.

The web-based guidance tool, developed initially through the EU FP7 project GUIDEnano¹⁶ and further optimized and expanded in several additional projects (including NanoCommons), allows for a complete RA for NMs and similar products from their production to their waste management. It includes an extensive list of more than 200 processes that are involved throughout the NMs' life cycle to choose from and to further specify the exposure conditions, such as the volume and the compartments of space in which the release of the NM happens and the relevance to the NM source and the presence of exposure controls. The GUIDEnano tool performs elaborate external exposure simulations that could provide Predicted Environmental Concentrations (PEC) or human exposure concentration estimates depending on the route of exposure, for example, inhalation, dermal, or oral exposure and uptake.

In the proposed NanoCommons RA workflow, we introduced the concept of extending and tailoring the RA process to the specific characteristics of individuals, through the integration of physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models, which predict the internal exposure levels, i.e. the mass/concentration of the NMs that reaches the systemic circulation, the organs, and tissues of an individual, following the injection, ingestion, or inhalation of the NM. Consequently, for more precise risk estimation, the actual internal exposure levels of tissues that might be severely affected by the exposure can be obtained using the appropriate PBPK model for the specific organism (and NM). This type of modeling can be performed on an individual basis, by incorporating toxicokinetic information about the substance, such as the adsorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) processes, as well as somatometric, and physiological parameters of the exposed individual (sex, age, Body Mass Index), in order to derive the NM concentrations in various body compartments.

For estimating the hazard Reference Points (RPs), the NanoCommons RA workflow includes three hazard quantification approaches:

- The Benchmark Dose (BMD) modeling approach, that can be applied to available dose-response data;
- The Read-across and/or nano Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship (QSAR) approach assuming the availability of relevant fully validated predictive models;
- The GUIDEnano similarity module and reference database, which provides a list of Final Safety Limit Values (FSLVs), which depend on the exposure setting and the RA hypothesis.

When internal exposure levels can be obtained using the PBPK model, tissue specific RPs should be acquired to provide local threshold limits that define safe use and exposure levels for the specific NM. For this purpose methodologies that stem from the dose-dependent nature of the molecular level perturbations, caused by the NM exposure, such as coupling BMD modelling with toxicogenomics data analysis via the Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) concept, are used to calculate Mechanism-of-Action (MOA)-related points of departure (PODs). This is described in greater detail in the case study implementation.

¹⁶ <https://www.guidenano.eu/>

4.4.3 Safe industrial production case study, based on the NanoCommons RA workflow

In the current case study, we implement a process related SbD strategy at the occupational settings to reduce the emissions and consequently exposure during manufacturing. It should be noted that other types of SbD strategies can be implemented in the RA models. When developing case studies, one of the main challenges is data availability. As more and more data are collected/stored/gathered in the NanoCommons KB, the applicability of the RA models will increase. The case study considered was the inhalation of TiO₂ NMs (JRC NM 102) aerosol by workers performing TiO₂ pouring in paint factories. Four scenarios of exposure were developed to obtain four different realistic doses for the workers. The risk of lung fibrosis (AOP173¹⁷) was assessed on the mouse model. Only the exposure scenario with the highest doses presented a risk. Specifically, case 1, involved the release of 45 g of TiO₂ in the air from pouring TiO₂ powder over 7 hours in the NF for an activity duration of 1 min by hours resulted in risk of perturbing the chemokine signaling pathway. In more detail, under this scenario, a mouse inhales TiO₂ by staying, for every hour, 90 s in the NF and the rest of the hour in the far field (FF). This movement pattern is repeated until the end of the 8 h work shift. The internal exposure for mice is simulated using the PBPK model, which has been developed and implemented in the Jaqpot platform. The RA is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of TiO₂ concentration in the lung with PODs that have been computed using a gene expression analysis workflow. The user can select the POD of interest among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defines the POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effect. Figure 17 presents the external and internal exposure generated when a 40 g mouse inhales the TiO₂ NM produced by case 1 and the movement pattern between NF and FF described above, while Figure 18 illustrates the risk of perturbing the chemokine signalling pathway under case 1 for a 40 g mouse.

Figure 17. External and internal exposure for a 40 g mouse, under the exposure setting produced by case 1.

¹⁷ <https://aopwiki.org/aops/173>

Risk assessment: Is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of TiO₂ concentration in the lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been computed using a [gene expression analysis workflow](#). The user can select the POD of interest among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defines the POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

Pathways: Chemokine signaling pathway

Time: Median pathway BMDt (1d p.e.)

logarithmic scale

Figure 18. Probability density function of the mass of TiO₂ in the lungs (black curve) after the 8h occupational exposure and BMDt value (red line) for Case 1, for a mouse weighing 40 gr, chemokine signalling pathway, 1d p.e.

In this case study, a safe by design strategy is described (supporting the NanoReg2 pillar 3, safer industrial production) which focuses on the activity of pouring TiO₂ and, more specifically, in altering the process features of case 1, in order to mitigate the risk of perturbing the chemokine signaling pathway. Other strategies could link to use other NMs, or NMs with coating or under a liquid state for example. Five different scenarios were used, with all of them affecting the NMs release concentration in the NF and so the corresponding external exposure for mice. All SbD scenarios involve the modification of the GUIDEnano parameters, whereas the parameters of the other models remained unchanged.

SbD scenario 1 involves the increase of the air exchange rate in the FF from 4 to 5. These parameters have been determined from the CaLIBRAte project as one of the main parameters driving the particle concentration over time during aerosol generation. Similarly, in SbD scenario 2, the air exchange rate parameter was tuned and this time increased from 4 to 15 (Table 6).

Table 6. An example of typical air exchange rates in a diverse environment¹⁸.

Building / Room	Air Change Rates - n - (1/hr)
All spaces in general	min 4
Attic spaces for cooling	12 - 15
Auditoriums	8 - 15
Bakeries	20
Banks	4 - 10
Barber Shops	6 - 10
Bars	20 - 30
Beauty Shops	6 - 10

¹⁸ <https://www.ihconstruction.com/archives/402>

SbD scenarios 3, 4 and 5 were developed using local control measures. The activity of TiO₂ pouring was initially performed in NF without any physical barrier with the FF. A partially enclosed area, a mobile local ventilation and a specialized ventilation for clean zone workers were implemented to control the aerosol concentration in the NF for the SbD scenarios 3, 4 and 5, respectively. The efficiency of this measure was obtained using the data in Table 7 extracted from Fransman *et al* (2008).

Table 7. Efficiency of different risk mitigation measures used to develop the safe by design scenario 3, 4 and 5 (extracted from Fransman *et al.* (2008)).

RMM	<i>n</i> ^a	Estimated efficacy ^b (%)	95% confidence interval (%)
Enclosure	14	50	4 to 74
Complete	3	86	30 to 97
Partial	6	23	-103 to 70
LEV	280	82	78 to 84
Exterior	65	81	75 to 86
LEV + enclosure	9	86	69 to 94
Integrated	133	87	84 to 90
Mobile	4	61	-28 to 88
Vapour collection	19	64	23 to 83
Specialized ventilation	14	87	73 to 94
Specialized booth	1	94	37 to 99
Clean-zone worker	6	86	64 to 95
Miscellaneous	7	85	47 to 96
General ventilation	42	43	17 to 61
Natural	9	31	-56 to 70
Mechanical	31	46	17 to 65
Suppression techniques	69	83	77 to 88
Wet suppression	32	84	75 to 89
Capture sprays	25	88	80 to 93
Stabilization	12	58	-3 to 83
Separation of workers	14	87	71 to 94
Complete	9	90	75 to 96
Partial	5	71	-31 to 94

Using the GUIDEnano tool, the 5 SbD modifications on case 1 were represented in the generated emission concentration - time profiles of the NF and FF regions. Following that, for each SbD scenario, the two curves were merged into one using the rationale described in 4.4.3, in order to simulate the desired mouse movement. The final concentration-time profiles of the 5 SbD scenarios are presented in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Combined NF and FF concentration-time profiles of TiO₂ for Safe by Design scenarios 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5.

The resulting external exposure, internal exposure and risk assessment modules of the RA tool after applying SbD strategies 1 to 5 are presented in Figures 20-24. All but the first strategy managed to mitigate the risk of perturbing the chemokine signaling pathway. Specifically, the most successful strategy was the application of a specialized ventilation for clean zone workers, followed by the utilization of a mobile local ventilation.

NanoCommons Risk Assessment Tool

Short description

The workflow is a combination of nanoinformatics tools available through the NanoCommons computational infrastructure. This web application, hosted and implemented within [Enalos Cloud Platform](#), estimates the risk of triggering AOP 173 (Lung Fibrosis) in mice due to exposure to 20nm TiO₂ engineered nanoparticles.

External exposure: Four different exposure scenarios have been simulated using the [GUIDENano tool](#). The user can alternatively enter a custom-made scenario.

Safe By Design scenario 1
 Case 1 with ventilation in the FF increased from 4 to 5 (air exchange rate)
 Download timeseries

Internal exposure: Concentration-time profiles for mice are simulated using a PBPK model which has been developed and implemented in the [Jaaprot platform](#). A plot depicting the mass-time profile in the lung is automatically generated.

Weight (5 - 50 grams) 40
 Compute

Risk assessment: Is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of concentration in the lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been cc using a [gene expression analysis workflow](#). The user can select the POD of among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defi POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

Pathways Chemokine signaling pathway
 Time Median pathway BMDI (1d p.e)
 logarithmic scale

Figure 20. External exposure, internal exposure and risk assessment modules for SbD scenario 1.

NanoCommons Risk Assessment Tool

Short description

The workflow is a combination of nanoinformatics tools available through the NanoCommons computational infrastructure. This web application, hosted and implemented within [Enalos Cloud Platform](#), estimates the risk of triggering AOP 173 (Lung Fibrosis) in mice due to exposure to 20nm TiO2 engineered nanoparticles.

External exposure: Four different exposure scenarios have been simulated using the [GUIDENano tool](#). The user can alternatively enter a custom-made scenario.

Safe By Design scenario 2
 Case 1 with ventilation in the FF increased from 4 to 15 (air exchange rate)
 Download timeseries

Internal exposure: Concentration-time profiles for mice are simulated using a PBPK model which has been developed and implemented in the [Jagroot platform](#). A plot depicting the mass-time profile in the lung is automatically generated.

Weight (5 - 50 grams) 40
 Compute

Risk assessment: Is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of concentration in the lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been cc using a [gene expression analysis workflow](#). The user can select the POD of among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defi POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

Pathways Chemokine signaling pathway
 Time Median pathway BMDT (1d p.e)
 logarithmic scale

Figure 21. External exposure, internal exposure and risk assessment modules for SbD scenario 2.

NanoCommons Risk Assessment Tool

Short description

The workflow is a combination of nanoinformatics tools available through the NanoCommons computational infrastructure. This web application, hosted and implemented within [Enalos Cloud Platform](#), estimates the risk of triggering AOP 173 (Lung Fibrosis) in mice due to exposure to 20nm TiO2 engineered nanoparticles.

External exposure: Four different exposure scenarios have been simulated using the [GUIDE Nano tool](#). The user can alternatively enter a custom-made scenario.

Safe By Design scenario 3
 Case 1 with the activity in the NF performed in a partially enclosed area

Internal exposure: Concentration-time profiles for mice are simulated using a PBPK model which has been developed and implemented in the [Jagoot platform](#). A plot depicting the mass-time profile in the lung is automatically generated.

Weight (5 - 50 grams) 40

Risk assessment: Is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of concentration in the lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been α using a [gene expression analysis workflow](#). The user can select the POD of among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defi POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

Pathways: Chemokine signaling pathway
 Time: Median pathway BMDI (1d p.e)
 logarithmic scale

Figure 22. External exposure, internal exposure and risk assessment modules for SbD scenario 3.

NanoCommons Risk Assessment Tool

Short description

The workflow is a combination of nanoinformatics tools available through the NanoCommons computational infrastructure. This web application, hosted and implemented within [Enalos Cloud Platform](#), estimates the risk of triggering AOP 173 (Lung Fibrosis) in mice due to exposure to 20nm TiO2 engineered nanoparticles.

External exposure: Four different exposure scenarios have been simulated using the [GUTDENano tool](#). The user can alternatively enter a custom-made scenario.

Safe By Design scenario 4
 Case 1 with the activity performed under a mobile local ventilation
 Download timeseries

Internal exposure: Concentration-time profiles for mice are simulated using a PBPK model which has been developed and implemented in the [Jaopot platform](#). A plot depicting the mass-time profile in the lung is automatically generated.

Weight (5 - 50 grams) 40
 Compute

Risk assessment: Is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of concentration in the lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been cc using a [gene expression analysis workflow](#). The user can select the POD of among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defi POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

Pathways Chemokine signaling pathway
 Time Median pathway BMDt (1d p e)
 logarithmic scale

Figure 23. External exposure, internal exposure and risk assessment modules for SbD scenario 4.

D6.4 - Initial integration of decision support system for safe-by-design strategy

NanoCommons Risk Assessment Tool

Short description

The workflow is a combination of nanoinformatics tools available through the NanoCommons computational infrastructure. This web application, hosted and implemented within [Enalos Cloud Platform](#), estimates the risk of triggering AOP 173 (Lung Fibrosis) in mice due to exposure to 20nm TiO₂ engineered nanoparticles.

External exposure: Four different exposure scenarios have been simulated using the [GUIDE Nano tool](#). The user can alternatively enter a custom-made scenario.

Safe By Design scenario 5

Case 1 with the activity performed with specialized ventilation for clean zone worker)

Download timeseries

Internal exposure: Concentration-time profiles for mice are simulated using a PBPK model which has been developed and implemented in the [Jaaprot platform](#). A plot depicting the mass-time profile in the lung is automatically generated.

Weight (5 - 50 grams) 40

Compute

Risk assessment: Is performed by comparing the predicted distribution of concentration in the lungs with Points of Departure (POD) that have been characterized using a [gene expression analysis workflow](#). The user can select the POD of among different pathways involved in AOP173 or the median value that defines POD of the AOP and short term (1 day) or long term (28 days) effects.

Pathways

Chemokine signaling pathway

Time

Median pathway BMDL (1d p.e)

logarithmic scale

Figure 24. External exposure, internal exposure and risk assessment modules for SbD scenario 5.

5. Conclusions

Sections 1-3 of this report provided a summary of the different safe-by-design concepts. What emerges from this analysis is that there has been a lot of great work, but that this is still somewhat disconnected and a clear vision for how to implement it practically remains elusive. Our next steps within NanoCommons will be to develop a map of the SbD universe with all the definitions given in sections 1 to 3 of the current deliverable and map these to the integrated tools developed in NanoCommons (as described in section 4). This would then also show those parts of the SbD concept that are not (completely) covered by the available services, and allow the ongoing SbD projects to begin to plug these gaps, with support from NanoCommons, for example, via additional TA projects. The co-developed map could also be used to evaluate the developed services and propose a roadmap (spatial as well as temporal) to prioritise the integration of the tools and how they should be combined to generate the largest benefits for the nanosafety community.

In the context of the NanoCommons project, a large number of tools of relevance to SbD have been developed and tested. This deliverable describes specifically how several tools can be used separately or in an integrated fashion to support the concept of SbD. At the highest level overview, we can state that the NanoCommons predictive models for safer product design (described in section 4.3) support NanoReg2's Pillar 1- safer materials and products by design, while the NanoCommons RA tools (described in section 4.4) relate to Pillar 3 - safer industrial production of the NanoReg2 approach. Currently, much of the functionality comes from GuideNano and as such there is additional work to be done to integrate other tools, such as the ECETOC tools for determining nanoforms, and the SIA toolbox where relevant. Thus, it is important to note that the current status only covers some parts of SbD and we will continue working to improve this.

In particular, nanoQSAR models can be utilized in Safer product design strategies. Given a toxicity related endpoint, nanoQSAR models can link the physicochemical characteristics of an NM to the biological response. Therefore, NM properties can be tested *in silico* before actually synthesizing them to ensure that they have the desired toxicological profile. The use of the Enalos Cloud platform innovation models was exploited in the area of SbD and exemplified to observe the effects of the different inputs (decorating molecule structures) on the prediction of CA binding to the MWCNTs and the toxicity of the resultant decorated-MWCNTs. In addition, a nanoQSAR model, hosted in the Jaqpot platform, was used to design metal oxide NMs with desired cytotoxicity profiles.

The integrated NanoCommons RA tools provide new functionalities of interest to a wide range of stakeholders, including risk assessors. By introducing AOPs into the RA workflows, risks can now be associated with the probability of triggering a MIE instead of the final AO, which is the current practice. We illustrated that protective measures taken through a SbD strategy managed to limit the NMs emission and exposure during the activity and led to a significant reduction for the worker's risks.

The ongoing SbD projects SAbYNA, ASINA and SABYDOMA are collaborating with NanoCommons via Transnational Applications (TA): The data produced during these projects will flow on the NanoCommons KB. Within NanoCommons, the challenge is to successfully streamline the available tools and provide easy, customized and integrative guidance on how to interconnect all the resources (databases, test protocols, models, tools, frameworks...) for assessing and managing the potential risks associated with nanotechnology-based products. Therefore, this collaboration with the SbD projects will facilitate the promotion of the NanoCommons KB infrastructure for SbD purposes and in general will support the safe design and use of NMs and nanotechnology-based products.

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